

Limits of Cognition and Insight

Wolfgang Sassin¹

Wolfgang Sassin,

Dr-Ing,
Independent researcher,
formerly Senior Scientist of International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
and Lecturer of Technical University Vienna
Austria

Article No and Translation / Номеръ статьи и переводъ: 010310202 ENG

For citation (Chicago style) / Для цитирования (стиль «Чикаго»):

Sassin, Wolfgang. 2018. "Limits of cognition and insight." *The Beacon: Journal for Studying Ideologies and Mental Dimensions* 1, 010310202.

Translation: English.

Translator: Wolfgang Sassin.

¹ Please send the correspondence to e-mail: w.sassin@aon.at.

Permanent URL links to the article:

HANDLE: 20.500.12656/thebeacon.1.010310202

<http://thebeacon.ru/pdf/Vol.%201.%20Issue%201.%20010310202%20ENG.pdf>

Received in the original form: 15 April 2018

Review cycles: 2

1st review cycle ready: 31 May 2018

Review outcome: 3 of 3 positive

Decision: To publish with minor revisions

2nd review cycle ready: 14 April 2018

Accepted: 18 April 2018

Translation ready: 24 April 2018

Published online: 24 April 2018

HEADLINE. Cognitive limitations and their logical consequences, Thinking in different dimensions.

ABSTRACT

Wolfgang Sassin. *Limits of Cognition and Insight.* In the paper, on the basis of discussing the analogy between geometry of geodesics and human cognition, the limits of cognition are discussed. An attempt to adapt human action to limited human perception can be found in the article. The problems shown therein, make it clear that the humanity needs a change in the mental coordinate system that refers to the very values that have led us to where we are right now, namely to a world in disarray.

Key words: geometric argumentation, ideological control, WE concept, stints of cognition, limits of insight, borders of consciousness

THE THIRD DIMENSION

THE THIRD DIMENSION, the view upwards into the sky has always had something fascinating about it. It helped man to orientate himself in a pristine nature not yet changed by him, not yet straightened and marked by artifacts. Gods seemed to play their intriguing games “up there,” untouched by clouds, storms, lightning and thunder.

The ancient Greeks believed that the sun god moved in his chariot over the firmament, a heavenly tent “firmly stretched out” above them. Venus, Mars, Jupiter, Pluto and other gods seemed to interfere with the lives of tiny humans, whose “horizon” reached as far as

their natural senses could reach and as far as their feet would take them. (Frazer 2012, vol. 2, 86–102). That was a few kilometers, at best a few hundred of them. With the domestication of the horse, man could then bridge greater distances and with the sailing ship it was possible to cross the seas and to reach unknown coasts. However to return, heaven's stars became indispensable. They offered the only firm and reliable order in a nature which could not change suddenly and unpredictably. The more closely one observed these stars, the more one could understand **time** as a phenomenon, as something that existed independently of day and night, and of the changing seasons. Calendars were created and people learned to look “into the future” and to orient their lives from the “here and now” to an ever more distant “there” and an ever more distant “tomorrow”. Instead of providence and fate, laws were formulated that connected causes and effects and allowed to “subdue” “the world” step by step.

Great hurdles on this long path of cognition and insight had to be overcome whenever irregularities in this third dimension were discovered. These were first comets, later the strange movements of Venus, Mars, Jupiter and the more distant planets of our solar system. Natural sciences finally dethroned these “gods” and revolutionised whole images of the world and the associated edifices of belief (Yates 1979, 116).

Fig. 1. The three-dimensional model of space-time continuum near our Sun.

© T. Pyle / Caltech / MIT / LIGO Lab

With the discovery of relativistic effects in the macrocosm and the duality of waves and particles in the microcosm, physics encountered two new cognitive hurdles in the 20th

century (De Broglie 1954, 8; Fairbank et al. 1988, 132–133, 155). They amount to nothing less than the overthrowing the “common sense.” The theory of relativity, much like quantum theory, has given new dimensions to space and time which we can no longer reconcile with those experiences our natural senses seem to teach us.

In order to get an idea of the four-dimensional space, i.e. the space-time continuum, physicists, in their capacity as “normal” human beings, therefore make use of a three-dimensional model. A rubber membrane with a regular grid on which a heavy sphere is placed illustrates the curvature of space caused by heavy masses. The weight of the sphere deforms the two-dimensional rubber membrane and distorts the originally rectangular network of straight lines (Fig. 1). However, we only recognize that these lines are no longer “straight” because we look at the two-dimensional membrane from an “overlying” third dimension and additionally imagine a beam of light running “straight” along one of these lines. Only from this “elevated” observation position do we assume that we can look around a “black hole” and see objects that should be hidden by this invisible hole.

If one follows this suggestive “explanation,” one may miss on the one hand,

1. that a flat being, which exists only in two spatial dimensions, could not even perceive the curvature of the membrane and therefore would not even come up with the idea of a “black hole”;
- on the other hand,
2. that on the assumption that the speed of light is constant, two synchronous light rays which run along adjacent lines passing the gravitational center “black hole” must be shifted against each other in time, because two adjacent lines in the vicinity of the “distortion” do have different lengths.

If one takes point 2 seriously, then one could conclude from the observation of a time shift in the propagation of two “parallel” light beams that the mass of the black hole “bends” time and not space. Or vice versa, one would see two different time phases of one and the same object at the same time.

So what now?

THE CHOICE OF REFERENCE FRAMES

THERE IS ANOTHER PARADOX that is rooted in our perceptual apparatus, which is located between quantum theory and relativity theory. Our brain perceives the world by separating itself from it, i.e. taking up a unique individual position of observation and assuming that it is unaffected by everything that happens “out there.” Exactly this means that human perception depends on the assumption that there is a **fixed and absolute point, in space as well as in time**, from which changes in the world can be grasped by an observer. But that is not the case.

Perception research has clearly confirmed: The brain needs time to grasp sensory information, to process it and produce a conscious impression. It averages sensory infor-

mation of less than about 1/10 of a second and even manipulates it, as can be demonstrated by optical and acoustic illusions. There is no fixed point in the universe, there are only dynamically changing relative references to other moving “points.” So what does $c = \text{constant}$ mean, where c represents the constant speed of light which, according to Einstein, unambiguously “defines” the relationship between *mass* and *energy* by the formula $E=mc^2$?

A completely different topic urges itself in this context. **If one simply imagines another “flat” universe, i.e. not a stretched flat rubber membrane, but a kind of balloon that is continuously inflated,** then the distance between all the points to be marked on its surface increases continuously. Such a model universe is curved and therefore finite. It can enlarge or reduce its two-dimensional surface. If there are “forces of attraction” between individual points on this surface, then the effect of this gravitation would decrease with the square of the distance between masses, according to what we measure in small cosmic distances according to Newton’s model. The imaginary balloon would expand faster and faster at the same charge pressure. Again another basic question arises whether there can be a “constant” speed of light at all, if the scale is distorted only from the point of view of an observer, who is mentally “above” the surface of the balloon and is not affected himself by the expansion.

In a very general way, and not only in this model, the question arises: What is “inertial mass,” i.e. the derived “counterforce” that counteracts the instantaneous change of a mass point by gravity? Is this mass inertia absolute or relative, i.e. does it decrease in proportion to the decreasing gravitational pull with a constantly increasing volume of the imaginary balloon?

Such a consideration leads to another paradox. If the masses causing “gravitation” are equally distributed on the surface of the balloon, then no measurable “gravity” can work at any single point at all. Because the effect of the gravitation of a particular neighbor in one direction would be compensated completely by the effect of the gravitation of the opposite neighbor.

Such a consideration leads to another paradox. If the masses causing “gravitation” are equally distributed on the surface of the balloon, then no measurable “gravity” can work at any single point at all. Because the effect of the gravitation of a particular neighbor in one direction would be compensated completely by the effect of the gravitation of the opposite neighbor.

Fig. 2. The models of the flat Universe as a balloon that is continuously inflated: a sphere (higher pane) or hyperboloid (lower pane).

© Henning Dalhoff / Science Photo Library

Fig. 3. Discontinuous transition from a two-dimensional to a one-dimensional “reality”.

Only a disturbance of an originally conceived homogenous mass or energy distribution (the latter because of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and Einstein's mass and energy equivalent) can lead to **many-particle systems**, which cause “density fluctuations” resulting in the emergence of discrete mass accumulations. The existence of stars and galaxies appear plausible only as a result of a kind of chain reaction of an initial minor disruption. However, many-particle systems are basically intransitive. They cannot be traced back to a “single cause.” Their behavior is chaotic and indeterminate in the long run.

The logically compelling argument of the abolition of gravity in a “finite” and “curved” universe evenly filled with “mass” in connection with the obvious many-particle systems, those of micro-phenomena, from atoms, via

molecules to “irregularly distributed macroscopic masses,” even to black holes, pose the deepest challenge to our cognitive processes and human logic. **The following two diagrams illustrate the role of thinking in dimensions and the conscious or unconscious choice of an observer’s “point of view.”**

The Euclidean geometry “emerged” from within the practically two-dimensional habitat of the Earth’s surface. For a long time it was unclear whether the earth was a flat disk or a kind of sphere. Let us therefore look at **Fig. 3**. If one enlarges an arbitrary triangle on the curved earth surface represented there, characterized by the points A, B and C, then with increasing size of this triangle it turns out not only that the sum of the inner angles violates the finding of Euclid: they do not add up to 180°. This violation does not occur because the connecting lines between the corner points of “tiny triangles” appear as straight lines. In fact, they are always parts of large circles. The reason for the deviation from Euclid’s rule is rather the use of two-dimensional angular measurement devices, i.e. of “geo-triangles” and tiny sections of the curved surface that fit the extent of the human perceptual horizon to be surveyed and measured.

Beyond that, **Fig. 3** illustrates a far more significant hurdle for our “logical” thinking which is limited by completely different dimensions. By these other “**dimensions**” the fundamental difference between macro- and micro-worlds is meant, i.e. by what we call one-, two-, three-, four- or even multi-dimensional systems.

This can be demonstrated by a very simple change in Fig. 3. If one moves the corner point B of the triangle A-B-C on the curved two-dimensional spherical surface until the leg C-B at point B2 meets the arch on which the leg A-C lies, then the triangle suddenly and

discontinuously changes into a “Zweieck” (biangle). The sum of angles of $180^\circ+x^\circ$ suddenly not only shrinks to 0° . A one-dimensional “curved” straight line A-B2 is created discontinuously from a two-dimensional surface. The corner point C dissolves.

And that is not all.

Fig. 4 also illustrates the possible sudden “disappearance” of a triangular surface by the simple attempt to enlarge it further and further. If one extends the leg A-B in the direction of B1, the area of the triangle grows continuously. Depending on the angle at point A, a triangle A-B1-C can reach up to half the surface of the sphere if the extension of the leg A-B is continued into the vicinity of point B2.²

With the transition from a two-dimensional structure into a one-dimensional one (illustrated in Fig. 3), i.e. from a “macroscopic” quality *triangle* into a quality of a *straight line* a discontinuous “**quantum leap**” to zero emerges in the area of the curved triangle. In Euclid's flat geometry this effect is inconceivable. There, a linear extension of the leg A-B would lead to infinity, and the triangle would grow continuously beyond all boundaries.

Figs 3 and 4 together therefore make it clear that, depending on the dimensions envisaged, “**new realities**” can arise, phenomena which we have not yet been able to imagine with the continuous extension within the dimensions “space” and “time” either in the direction of “zero” or in the direction of “infinity.” Of course, mathematics is also caught up in this dilemma, regardless of whether “infinite series” can be calculated with arbitrary accuracy. *Zero* and *Infinity* are not results of mathematics, they are part of the intellectual foundation on which mathematics was built and operates.

Fig. 3 also provides an indication of an error or, rather, of an unfounded presumption associated with the notion of a “first beginning” or a “last end.” Zero and infinity, the two sides of eternity, form a black hole for human knowledge. Fig. 3 also shows this quite clearly.

The result of the extension of the triangle leg A-B in Fig. 3 to point B2 produces a distance that begins at point A and ends at point B2. In this one-dimensional world A-B2 there is only a seemingly irrevocable beginning and an end. If, however, one extends this

Fig. 4. “Quantum effect”.
Discontinuous change of a “macroscopic” quality.

² At the moment the leg A-B of the triangle crosses the arc determined by the leg A-C at point B2, the finite surface of the “triangle” collapses, because the shortest distance of the two points A and B shifts discontinuously to the opposite side of the spherical half of this curved 2-dimensional world. A new triangle A-B3-C emerges. In between these two different states of both triangles with an inverted symmetry, point C disappears for an infinitely small moment and a curved one-dimensional line A-B2 separates the “old” and the “new” two-dimensional triangles.

limited supposed straight line A-B2, the “end” B2 finally meets the starting point A again – surprisingly and suddenly in a finite “distance” which is determined by the curvature of the two-dimensional spherical surface. Also the “direction” of time one would like to fix in such a linear world suddenly dissolves in this case. To put it allegorically, the way forward does not lead into the future, but into the past, or vice versa. Because the view “forward” meets the “observer” himself from “behind,” no matter in which direction he looks.

FROM SCIENTIFIC MULTIPLE DIMENSIONS TO SOCIAL MULTIPLE DIMENSIONS

IF ONE SUMMARIZES THE “EXPERIENCES” of this fictitious excursion into the two-dimensional but curved world of a “balloon”, which is viewed from a superordinate third dimension, then many of the current problems and challenges of a complex global reality become clear almost by themselves. This applies not only to cosmology.

Dark matter and *dark energy* are reminiscent of hurdles to recognition emerging with increasing distance to tried and tested scales, scales from a “near” world that we have learned to grasp with our natural senses. Relativity theory and quantum theory are therefore theories which, although they represent an approximation to reality, have not yet been united and probably will never be.

Fig. 5. The schematics of the Big Bang in the human understanding. This schematics clearly demonstrates the “mono-humanism” concept.

© Open University; BANTAM www.bantam.anspack.de

Other theoretical edifices, such as the “circumstantial evidence” “condensing” astronomy into a Big Bang, as well as “monotheism” and “monohumanism” intertwined with it, try to find a sole final cause for the emergence of “the world and man.” For this reason alone, both are edifices of faith, each in its own way.

After all, not only scientific theories, but also all modern social theories are based on experiments that inevitably lead to ever larger and unknown territories and dimensions. This applies to the characteristics and abilities of the individual. It also applies to the behavior of ever larger and ever more inhomogeneous crowds and their ability to perceive and reflect.

If, in the past, new dimensions became accessible through new techniques, through new methods of measurement and documentation, for example through the invention of writing, then the ideas of the humanities and social sciences had to be changed regularly, if not completely discarded and sometimes replaced by radically different ones.

The emergence of a completely new phenomenon in evolution, such as “**artificial**” **intelligence**, falls into such a category of fundamental change that demands a redefinition of the individual and, consequently, of *homo sapiens*. The consequences of the transition from Ptolemy to Galileo's world view on religious convictions and the splitting of Christianity reveal which “inner” interdependencies always exist between worldly and spiritual edifices of belief. Galileo contributed decisively to the dispute over the right “images of God and Man.” And at that time this dispute got quite out of control.

The current attempt to introduce **democracy on a global level** is undoubtedly such a new daring experiment, which not only questions existing images of man but is likely to lead to profound revolutions. Galilei and Kepler have moved the sun into the centre of “the world” instead of the earth. A “world order” based on grassroots democracy would have similar consequences. Instead of the individual, “humanity” is now suddenly propagated as the centre of thought and the core of every ethic order. **Humanity, not the individual, influences the climate.**

The idea of a global democracy implicitly associated with this shift of “identities” is the result of linear thinking. It ignores the complexity, the multidimensionality of the phenomenon *life* as a whole, a phenomenon that evolution has produced. And this linear thinking, recognizable by repeatedly celebrated *steps in the right direction*, creates situations that, as sketched in Figs 3 and 4, must lead to surprising tipping points. A minimal disturbance at any point of leg A-B2 of the original triangle A-B-C in Fig. 3, shrunk to a one-dimensional line, cannot only lead to a new point C'. Suddenly, as a veritable *quantum effect*, a new surface of unpredictable size may unfold. Since this minimal disturbance can also make accessible the “other side” of the two-dimensional surface of a sphere, a mirror-inverted symmetry can also result for a two-dimensional structure A-B2-C'.

Straight lines, lines in whatever form curved, as well as elementary planes and “spaces,” more so symmetries are extremely rare “elements” of the real world. They are abstract elements of human thought like the *horizon*, like “sunbeams” in backlight or parts of a landscape reflected by untroubled water surfaces. This also applies to every kind of “shape.” With the help of such logically intertwined mental elements, our neural networks, that is what

we call the brain, construct an extremely reduced image of an utterly complex external reality. The excursion into the three-dimensional “geometry” of Figs 3 and 4 therefore reveals the limits of human knowledge in general. Not only in mathematics and physics, but in the natural sciences in general, “surprises” always occur in the imaging of external reality when “horizons” are extended, especially when a first or a last cause is inferred starting from the direct and familiar of our everyday experience and heading towards the greater whole, or in the opposite direction towards the very small.

These “geometric” examples shed light on the limits of human cognition and insight. Combined with the consequences of “flat thinking,” without which a complex external reality cannot be reduced and “made conscious,” it is not surprising that the humanities in particular are much more severely restricted than the natural sciences by this mental limitation. Rationality, emotionality and communication between individual brains that reconstruct external reality individually require a far greater reduction in collective behavior and collective phenomena than Newton's derivation of the laws of gravity from the “logical interpretation” of an apple falling to the ground **in an otherwise empty universe** (Newton 1999, 406 and further), a situation that is in conflict with reality.

TO A SECOND ENLIGHTENMENT?

THAT ONLY SIMPLE “STORIES” ASSOCIATE HUMAN COMMUNITIES – beginning from two-way relationships over families and clans up to whole “peoples” – to those special WEs, which then act jointly and uniformly, is an undeniable necessity resulting from the most different images of reality, which social beings „paint“ each for themselves. Only “simple stories,” stereotypes, be it images of man or images of the world, can be shared. Therefore, in order to win rather dissimilar individuals for alternative concepts of WEs and to be able to “lead” them collectively, “simple challenges” are needed. Only basic human conditions such as hunger, helplessness as the inability to “find one’s way” without the help of others, both in a material and a mental sense, can easily be communicated between “individuals.” These are conditions that can be associated with birth and death, with illness and with events or circumstances that require basic trust between individuals.

If such a group of WEs gets into a situation, which extends sufficiently beyond regularly recurring and shared common experiences, or in which conditions so far perceived as positive turn into negative through an excess of repetition or densification, then the simple and shared “stories,” those narratives which “create” images of the world and of man, lose their power of persuasion. This applies to religious communities as well as to “political communities.”

The extension of *the rule of the people* in the direction of a global rule, a rule of mankind, represents such a dimensional change. Global democracy, humanity as an all-encompassing community thought to its logical end, finally assumes a single undivided will which would have a singular meta-consciousness as its prerequisite, a will which finds its expression in

Mono-humanism, namely in the assertion that all human beings are equal. The story of the mythical Noah and his Ark, who had to decide whom to take on board and whom not, is not the only illustration of the intellectual labyrinth into which the narrative of the One Humanity can lead, i.e. the idea that we are all sitting in a common Spaceship Earth.

The fact that the narrative of an impending climate catastrophe distracts from other, much more urgent “catastrophes,” which among other things are triggered by the belief in economic growth as the very prerequisite for social peace, is one of those dimensional reductions described above using the example of a “curved geometry.” The same applies to the notion that urbanization makes people free, or even that the serious consequences of demographic imbalances can be avoided by migration.

A second enlightenment seems overdue in view of the complexity of the globally interlinked artificial bases of life of nearly 8 billion individuals, who can no longer grasp this complexity, and equally critical, in view of the hardly controllable technical means of power in the hands of a few “representatives” of these 8 billion.

Whether such a Second Enlightenment will come about or not, the mental climate on this planet is likely to change faster, more profoundly and more discontinuously than the physical climate.

The dramatic consequences of a global mental climate catastrophe can certainly not be prevented by “taxes” on the “emission” of new people, nor by the “censorship” of heretical thoughts by New Speak and the introduction of Truth Ministries, as George Orwell did already demonstrate 70 years ago (Orwell 1949). There is a need for a convincing vision of the future. That is an unambiguous description of the duties to be fulfilled before any rights can emerge, which must ensure order on those civilizational platforms that always need to be erected and maintained by hard work. This multifaceted Anthropocene is not based on a *Creation* donated to all, it is no common good but the property of those only who are able to create and defend their sustainable civilizational living platforms.

An attempt to reconcile human actions with the limits of human cognition and insight can be found in the book *Evolutionary Environments - homo sapiens an Endangered Species?* which interlinks different cultures and perspectives (Sassin et al. 2018). The problems highlighted therein demonstrate that we need to change our mental coordinate system, which is oriented precisely by those values that have led us to where we are now, namely in a *World in Disarray*. This applies to the “natural” sciences, as well as to the “spiritual” sciences, the religious as well as the political images of the world and of man. We all have to realize that the values of a world that is disappearing because it is overloaded, deprive us, *homo sapiens*, of the very *sapiens* that distinguishes us from our animal predecessors, the *homos*. The *homo billionis*, the new conviction that focuses on the survival of humanity and its well-being and spreads everywhere, it reduces the individual to a being that is part of a gigantic herd. Herds always panic, too narrowly confined, and not only elude any rational control. They rather lose their emotional, i.e. their “human” qualities, which have developed solely from the experience of free individuals working together and against each other.

How to avoid a **mental climate catastrophe** within the next one or two generations, in view of the additional billions of *homos* expected by then, is the real challenge we face. It is this mental climate change, not a physical climate change, by whatever triggered, that threatens the future of mankind. In order to be able to face this challenge at all, we as a group of distinct societies must become aware of the limits of our different cognitive abilities. Otherwise, so it seems, we prepare for ourselves a fate that once befell the dinosaurs. Not the planet must be saved, but the *Sapiens* must be protected from its archaic heritage the *Homo*.

REFERENCES

- De Broglie, Louis. 1954. *The Revolution in Physics*. London: Routledge.
- Fairbank, J. D., Michelson, P. F., and C. W. Everitt, eds. 1988. *Near Zero: New Frontiers of Physics*. New York: W. H. Freeman and Co.
- Frazer, James George, Sir. 2012. *The Golden Bough*, in 12 vols. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, Isaac. 1999 [1687]. *The Principia: Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy*. Transl. by I. B. Cohen and A. Whitman, with a Guide by I. B. Cohen. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Orwell, George [Blair, Eric A.]. 1949. *Nineteen Eighty Four*. London: Secker and Warburg.
- Sassin, Wolfgang, Donskikh, Oleg, Gnes, Alexandre, Komissarov, Sergey, and Depei Liu. 2018. *Evolutionary Environments. Homo Sapiens - an Endangered Species?* Innsbruck: Studia Universitätsverlag.
- Yates, Frances A., Dame. 1979. *Giordano Bruno and the Hermetic Tradition*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

EXTENDED SUMMARY

SASSIN, WOLFGANG. LIMITS OF COGNITION AND INSIGHT.

WITH SEVERAL GEOMETRIC EXAMPLES WITH SPHERES AND GEODESICS, the complexity of multidimensional thinking is demonstrated in the article.

The geometric examples described and analysed, shed some light on the limits of human cognition and insight. Combined with the consequences of "flat thinking," without which a complex external reality cannot be reduced and "made conscious," it is not surprising that the humanities are much more severely restricted than the natural sciences by the mental limitations. Rationality, emotionality and communication between individual brains that re-construct external reality individually, require a far greater reduction in collective behaviour and collective phenomena than Newton's derivation of

the laws of gravity from the “logical interpretation” of an apple falling to the ground in an otherwise empty universe, a situation that is in conflict with reality. The mental limitations of cognition and insight lead to the emergence of ideological control over the borders of human cognition.

As a result, concepts of global democracy, monohumanism, the Spaceship Earth, arose. The extension of the rule of the people in the direction of a global rule, a rule of mankind, represents such a dimensional change. Global democracy, humanity as an all-encompassing community thought to its logical end, finally assumes a single undivided will which would have a singular meta-consciousness as its prerequisite, a will which finds its expression in Mono-humanism, namely in the assertion that all human beings are equal. The story of the Biblical hero, patriarch Noah and his Ark, who had to decide whom to take on board and whom not, is not the only illustration of the intellectual labyrinth into which the narrative of the One Humanity can lead, i.e. the idea that we are all sitting in a common Spaceship Earth. The fact that the narrative of an impending climate catastrophe distracts from other, much more urgent “catastrophes,” which among other things are triggered by the belief in economic growth as the very prerequisite for social peace, is one of those dimensional reductions described above using the example of a “curved geometry.” The same applies to the notion that urbanization makes people free, or even that the serious consequences of demographic imbalances can be avoided by migration.

The dramatic consequences of a global mental climate catastrophe can certainly not be prevented by “taxes” on the “emission” of new people, nor by the “censorship” of heretical thoughts by any variations of New Speak or Truth Ministries, as George Orwell did already demonstrate 70 years ago. There is a need for a convincing vision of the future, i.e. an unambiguous description of the duties to be fulfilled before any rights can emerge, which must ensure order on those civilisational platforms that always need to be erected and maintained by hard work. We all have to realise that the values of a world that is disappearing because it is overloaded, deprive us, *homo sapiens*, of the very *sapiens* part that distinguishes us from our animal predecessors, the *homos*. The *homo billionis*, the new conviction that focuses on the survival of humanity and its well-being and spreads everywhere, it reduces the individual to a being that is a part of a gigantic herd. Herds always panic, being too narrowly confined, and do not elude an ideological and rational control. But that is not the only consequence of their panic state. They rather lose their emotional, i.e. their “human” qualities, which have developed solely from the experience of free individuals working together and against each other.

The paper outlines the ways how to avoid a mental climate catastrophe within the next one or two generations, in view of the additional billions of *homos* expected by then, but certainly does not give any recipes and prescriptions. It is a real challenge for all of us.

Author / Авторъ

Dr-Ing Wolfgang Sassin's teaching, research, advisory activities and affiliations included the Technical University of Vienna (Austria), the Research Centre Jülich (Germany), IIASA (Austria), the International Panel on Climate Change IPCC, the UN Program Habitat, the Directorate General on Research and Innovation of the European Commission (Belgium), and OEMs in the German automobile industry on man-machine interfaces.

Wolfgang Sassin,
Independent researcher,
Jochberg 5
6335 Thiersee
Austria

© Wolfgang Sassin
Licensee The Beacon: Journal for Studying Ideologies and Mental Dimensions

Licensing the materials published is made according to Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence

